

**THE INFLUENCE OF THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ON THE UZBEK
ECONOMY**

Shamshiddinov Bakhriddin Sharobiddin o‘g‘li

Andijan Machine-Building Institute

Assistant of the Department of Humanities

baxriddinshamshiddinov@gmail.com

The oil and gas industry occupies one of the priority sectors in Uzbekistan's economy, as it largely ensures the well-being of the country's population and influences not only the country's economic development but also its security and energy independence. The oil and gas complex of Uzbekistan is considered one of the strategic sectors of the economy. Therefore, ensuring the effective development of this sector is an important task for the entire economic complex of our country. The republic ranks 10th in the world in gas production, with an annual oil production of about 5 million tons. In our country, oil and gas processing products are represented by a wide range of items that meet international quality standards. However, in recent years, the growing demand for oil, gas, and their products has necessitated an increase in oil refining volumes, which, in turn, requires the continuous development of new fields, maintenance of production in existing ones, as well as determining ways to improve the efficiency of oil refining and the development of reserves in these fields. All of this requires significant investment in the republic's oil and gas industry [1].

In this regard, research aimed at identifying the beneficial potential of the local complex to ensure priority investments for contributing to the long-term effective development of the entire oil and gas industry is of particular importance. This cannot be envisioned without employing a management approach based on strategic planning. The oil and gas industry is a strategically vital component of the

economic system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan, being part of the international economic community, could not remain unaffected. However, thanks to the comprehensive State Program for the Implementation of Anti-Crisis Measures, many problems that have arisen in several developed countries have been prevented. Most importantly, the stability of the national economy is maintained, as oil and gas companies have the opportunity to maximize their technological, financial, and intellectual resources to ensure sustainable economic growth. Uzbekistan's consistent presence in the oil and gas industry confirms not only the trust of foreign investors and the international reputation enjoyed by the republic's industrial sector, but also the fulfillment of all its obligations to the international community. The introduction of new equipment, advanced technologies, mechanization and automation of production processes, as well as the possibility of reconstructing and developing existing oil and gas fields, opens up a wide field of activity for foreign companies to invest. This comes with the prospect of increasing and upgrading gas processing production capacities to boost hydrocarbon production, as well as diversify gas chemical production [2].

In the coming years, Uzbekneftegaz National Holding Company plans to implement several infrastructure projects in the Kashkadarya region that will ensure the stability of natural gas production in the country. It should be noted that the industry is focused on deep processing of raw materials to fully utilize the existing potential. Thus, in collaboration with a consortium of Korean companies, a project is being implemented to build Central Asia's largest gas chemical complex based on the Surgil field on the Ustyurt Plateau. The complex's design capacity will allow processing 4 billion cubic meters of natural gas, producing 362 thousand tons of polyethylene and 83 thousand tons of polypropylene. Uzbekistan has great potential for industrial development, but in our opinion, only the proper development of the oil and gas sector will enable solving the problem of elevating Uzbekistan's economy to a new level while preserving achievements in other

sectors of the economy. The Republic of Uzbekistan needs to expand the range, quality, and production volume of petroleum products.

It can be concluded that the development of oil refining in the republic should proceed step-by-step along the following path: additional loading of existing oil refining capacities with domestically produced and imported raw materials, improvement of technology and deepening of oil refining processes, increasing the capacity of oil refineries, and reaching the level of one ton of refined oil per capita in the near future. Only under these conditions can the annual growth rates required by the country's economy be satisfied. The tasks are immense, but without improving the country's oil industry and fully meeting the economy's need for high-quality petroleum products, it is impossible to further develop the country [3].

REFERENCES

1. Ахмадалиев К.К. Проект: Повышение энергоэффективности промышленных предприятий. Ташкент, 2015. С. 78-85.
2. Салихов Н.М. Нефть и газ в зеркале планеты // Деловой мир, 2017. С. 10-12.
3. Ибрагимов Р.Р. Нынешняя ситуация и дальнейшая судьба нефтегазового сектора Узбекистана, 2015. С. 3-5.

